

THE INCLUSIVE EDUCATION NEXUS FOR SUSTAINABLE PUBLIC HIGHER EDUCATION IN WEST-CENTRAL AFRICA

Ngwa, Emmanuel Shu

Department of Educational Leadership, Faculty of Education, University of Bamenda, Cameroon
shuemma1987@gmail.com

Nyugap, Charly Ringyu

Department of Educational Psychology, University of Buea, Cameroon

Ogunji, Chinwe Victoria

Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education Alex Ekwueme Federal University, Ndufu-Alike, Ebonyi State, Nigeria

and

Takob, Clementine Seh

Centre for Teaching & Learning, National University of Lesotho, Lesotho

Abstract

The Inclusive Education (IE) innovation is seen as critical to achieving sustainable development. This is echoed in the Education 2030 Agenda, which provides guidance towards the accomplishment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all). Within the sphere of Higher Education (HE), this inclusive innovation bears an intense moral burden to sensitize and provide the knowledge, skills, and values required to attain a just, equitable and sustainable society. However, the principles of inclusion and equity have often been overshadowed by excellence and competitiveness. The notion of quality is mostly expressed in terms of university rankings in the various league tables. Consequently, it is necessary that the public HE be tailored towards serving a broader purpose beyond economic development. That is, combating national and international disparities and persistent gaps in the availability of higher education for the thousands of students from all facets of society. In this paper therefore, we examine the inclusive education nexus as a sustainability undertaking for public universities in West-Central Africa (Nigeria and Cameroon), with a focus on; access for all qualified, full participation in the teaching-learning process, and respect for diversity within the physical learning environment. It recommends practical steps and a strong political and moral will from all stakeholders towards the implementation of outstanding policy provisions on inclusive education in the public HE sector. This is critical in an era where inclusion is a strong indicator of quality education and sustainable development.

Keywords: Inclusive education; Sustainable public higher education; Higher education; West-Central Africa

Introduction

In 1948, the international community came together under the United Nations to adopt the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), basically in response to human rights abuses committed by belligerent parties during the Second World War. The severity of these violations made it necessary for a universal consensus to be adopted to explicitly define the basic inalienable human rights (freedom, justice and equality) that could apply to all peoples of the world, no matter their religious, socio-cultural, political, economic and physical backgrounds (Izuka, 2010). Even though the UDHR is not legally binding in itself, its ideals have however been given legal status in other UN

conventions and so are legally binding under international law. Such conventions include amongst others: The UN Convention against Discrimination in Education (1960), the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (United Nations, 1966a), the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (United Nations, 1966b) and the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) (United Nations, 2006).

The codification of human rights in law not only gives them validity but also raises them to the status of civil rights (basic constitutional rights of all citizens). For instance, the right to education as a civil right signifies the right to access quality education, and be respected within the learning environment (UNESCO, 2007). Consequently, it's the responsibility of all stakeholders to ensure that constitutional effort is made and measures put in place to guarantee equality and equitability treatment, concerning how educational opportunities are afforded and educational resources allocated to all citizens at all levels of education (UNESCO, 2004). This is particularly important in the higher education domain which has been variedly described as the support system of primary and secondary education (UNESCO, 2005), and empirically proven to be an engine of innovation with a positive correlation to the sustainable development of society (Fonkeng and Ntembe, 2009 and Bawakiyillenou et al. 2013). The impact of the; allocation of higher educational opportunities and resources, the roles of stakeholders and the treatment meted out to them within the educational system can be very huge. Therefore, seeing education as a basic human right creates a legal and moral foundation for inclusion at all levels – thus the concept of inclusive education (IE) in higher education.

As already established, an inclusive HE system has a significant role to play in the attainment of sustainable development. The preamble of the Sustainable Development Agenda (SDGs) opines clearly that member nations of the UN are determined to foster inclusive, just, equitable and peaceful societies (UNO, 2015). This means that there can be no sustainable development without inclusion, equity, justice and peace, and no society can be said to be inclusive, equitable, just and peaceful without being on the path to sustainability. This argument is critical because inclusion, justice, equity and peace are significant ingredients in the development of any contemporary society. Inclusive HE, as a fundamental ingredient of sustainability is therefore appropriately echoed in the Education 2030 Agenda, which provides a framework towards ensuring quality and equitable inclusive education and lifelong learning opportunities for all, and at all levels (SDG 4 – UN, 2015)

Inclusion in HE has often been overshadowed by excellence and competitiveness, and the notion of quality has mostly been expressed in terms of university rankings in various league tables (International Association of Universities –IAU, 2015). As stakeholders of HE it becomes very necessary that HE be directed towards serving a broader purpose beyond economic development. That is, combating national and international disparities in the availability of HE opportunities and resources for the ever-increasing student population (IAU, 2015). Theoretically underpinned by the Inclusive Lens Model (UNESCO, 2009) and the Triple Bottom Line Model of sustainability (Elkington, 1997), the authors examined the IE nexus as a sustainability undertaking for public universities in Nigeria. Focus was on; access to HE for all, inclusive participation in the teaching and learning process, and the respect for diversity in the physical learning environment.

Inclusive Education (IE) and Sustainable Higher Education (SHE)

Inclusive education is a United Nations innovation, as one of the major strategies aimed at addressing the global problems of marginalization, exclusion and discrimination, in response to the basic principle of Education for All (EFA). UNESCO, in 2009, referred to IE as a process that is concerned with the transformation of educational systems and institutions to handle the educational needs of all types and groups of learners. Similarly, Wiles and Bondi (2011), note that IE is about admitting special needs students into mainstream education settings, and providing support structures and services to them. It is not about bringing them into regular school settings to be

supported by unadjusted existing structures and services. Consequently, it is absolute to note that IE answers to the diverse needs of all learners through increased participation by all stakeholders and providing an enabling learning environment, thereby reducing exclusion from and within the education system (UNESCO).

Theoretically, this is supported by the UNESCO (2009) inclusive lens model whereby the school system is seen as being responsible for a student's inability to achieve his/her potential, rather than the student being responsible, as has been the case prior to inclusive education. Figure 1, shows an illustrative definition of the concept of inclusive education.

Figure 1: Illustrative definition of Inclusive Education

Source: Adapted from Izuka (2010)

United Nations agencies and member nations have over the years made great efforts in the advancement of IE both in policy and action. Some international legislations on inclusive education include among others: the 1990 Jomtien Declaration on Education For All (EFA), the UNESCO Salamanca statement (1994)- which admonishes governments to give the highest priority to inclusive education, the 2006 United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, which calls on member states to ensure an inclusive education practices at all levels, and the 2009 UNESCO Policy Guidelines on Inclusive Education.

Sustainable higher education (SHE)

SHE is inextricably linked to sustainable development. The concept of sustainable development came to light at the culmination of 1992 the Rio Earth Summit. The summit prioritized global environmental discussions and made

improvements to the framework put forward at the 1972 United Nations Conference on the Human Environment in Stockholm (Cleveland & Kubiszewski, 2007). The Brundtland Report (1987), supported by Johnston (2007) and Longshurt (2014), presents the most globally acclaimed meaning of sustainable development as; development that takes into account the desires of the present generation without undermining the ability of upcoming generations to meet their needs. That is when society can cater for the social, economic and environmental needs of the citizenry while also being conscious of the needs of the unborn citizens of that society.

John Elkington in his 1997 triple bottom line model of sustainability recognizes the importance of these three factors (social, economic and environmental) when he argued that; there is a need for business institutions, governments and NGOs to consider the economic, environmental and social dimensions of society in all their endeavours. According to Elkington (1997), triple bottom-line reporting can be a crucial tool to support sustainability goals by focusing on full investment results with regard to performance along the interconnected dimensions of profits, people and the planet. Figure 2 illustrates the triple bottom line model, showing the interactions of the three factors.

Figure 2: Graphic description of the triple bottom line Model
Source: Udandarao & Kuchibhotla (2016)

The recognition of the interconnection and interdependence of these three factors, coupled with the critical role of education, set the base for the 2005 declaration on education for sustainable development. This declaration named the ten years from 2005 and 2014, as the decade of education for sustainable development (Louw, 2013, UNESCO 2005, 2006b, and Longshurt, 2014). UNESCO (2006b) highlights that the 2005 declaration was aimed at:

Rethinking and revising education from nursery school to university to include a clear focus on current and future societies on the development of knowledge, skills, perspectives and values related to sustainability. This means reviews of existing curricula in terms of their objectives and content to develop trans-disciplinary understandings of social, economic

and environmental sustainability, and recommended and mandated approaches to teaching, learning and assessment. (p. 56)

According to UNESCO (2008), SHE therefore requires a reorientation of HE systems through large-scale shifts in curriculum priorities, especially in relation to teaching, research and outreach. It integrates the values, principles and practices of sustainable development into all facets of post-secondary or university education, with the idea that such inputs would spur behavioral changes that could likely lead to a more resilient future in the areas of economic viability, environmental integrity, and an equitable and just society for current and future generations (UNESCO, 2005b). Aina (2010), notes that sustainable higher education through its functions contributes to human capital development, the construction of socio-cultural values, and capacity formation for individual and collective emancipation from ignorance to domination. This has an important role to play in producing sustainable students and graduates with an understanding of the complexities, connections and interdependencies between the economy, social and environmental life (Elder, 2009).

The Problem of Inclusion in Public Higher Education in West-Central Africa

Nigeria is amongst the first countries in Africa to have started inclusive education by developing excellent laws in IE (Garruba, 2003). In the public HE sector, it is believed that some higher institutions of learning in the nation were already offering IE-related programs and services to persons and students with special needs, even before an official Federal Government Legislation on Special education (Garruba, 2003 and Ngwa, 2012). The University of Ibadan in 1976, is noted to have pioneered a Diploma in special education and a Bachelor's Program in 1976. The University of Jos in 1977 also commenced a Bachelors degree program in special needs education and a postgraduate programme in 1978. The FACT (Federal Advanced Teachers College, Special), now called the Federal College of Education, Special Oyo, was established by the federal government in 1977 and remains one of the few public colleges of special and inclusive teacher training in the whole of Sub-Saharan Africa (Garuba, 2003 and Nyugap, 2017).

Fakolade (2009), holds that the social service era of 1977, saw the release of the National Policy on Education (NPE), containing provisions and aims of IE in Nigeria, among which are to:

- Provide a deep meaning to the idea of equalizing educational opportunities for all children; their physical, mental and emotional disabilities notwithstanding,
- Make available adequate education for all special needs children and adults, so that they may be able to play their roles in contributing to the nation's development,
- Create opportunities for exceptional and gifted children to be able to develop their skills at their pace, for the good of the nation's economic and technological development plans.

Generally, Nigeria has ratified all international conventions and legislations on IE and has been able to contextualize these policies in her Education Policy (2004). It stipulates the inclusion of all children/students with special needs into mainstream schools, and free access to education for children with exceptionalities in schools (NPE, 2004).

However, the implementation of these policies has mostly been theoretical rather than practical, particularly within Nigerian Universities. Some scholars (Fokolade, 2009; Uchem, Ngwa and Asogwa, 2014) note that a lot has been done on inclusive education literature by African education scholars as compared to what is actually being practised in educational institutions. Ngwa (2012), supports that even some Nigerian public universities like the Universities

of Ibadan that had introduced academic programs in special/inclusive education long before the adoption of major international legislations on inclusion have not been able to put in place adequate practical measures to cater for special needs students. Consequently, it will not be an overstatement to deduce that; while most nations in advanced economies have gone beyond categorical provisions to full inclusion, West and Central African nations still appear to be grappling with the challenge of making available practical provisions for children with special needs, even on mainstreaming basis.

Inclusive Education-Sustainable Higher Education Nexus

The United Nations, through its education-related agencies like UNESCO has in recent years promoted global efforts by other Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), educational institutions and State governments in fostering the IE agenda in the higher education subsector. The creation of UNESCO-sponsored inclusive education centres within higher educational institutions, and the promotion and funding of research and capacity building on inclusive education around the globe (EFA Global Monitoring Report, 2015) and particularly across Sub-Saharan Africa are among practical efforts in the implementation and monitoring of inclusive education innovations (Uchem and Ngwa, 2014 & Nyugap and Ngwa, 2015).

For instance, setting up of the UNESCO Chair for Special Education at the University of Buea, Cameroon (2008) (a Resource Center for Special and Inclusive education), the organization of the 2010 International Workshop on Inclusive Education in Higher Education and the 2015 Inclusive Education Symposium for West and Central Africa - all funded by the UNESCO Chair for Special Education, University of Buea, in collaboration with the University administration and Cameroon's Ministry of Higher Education; are among UNESCO's recent practical steps towards promoting inclusive education in higher education in West and Central Africa (Nyugap and Ngwa, 2015). According to Izuka (2010) and Ngwa (2012), inclusive higher education demands improved access, and quality engagement in the teaching-learning process, and provides an enabling physical learning environment in a society yearning for sustainability, yet generally characterized by social exclusion.

In 2015, the UN adopted 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and its 169 targets, demonstrating the scale and ambition of the post-2015 world development Agenda. Goal 4 of the said agenda focuses on education: "*Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all*" (UN, 2015). Higher Education (HE) as the support base for basic and secondary education in any society (UNESCO, 2006) has a significant contribution to make in attaining this agenda. To prepare the groundwork towards the attainment of this goal, UNESCO in November 2015 adopted the Education 2030 Framework for Action. The President of the International Association of Universities (IAU), while speaking at the event, welcomed the key position HE occupies in the new agenda. According to IAU (2015:1), the implementation strategy for SDG 4, clearly articulates a number of essential values and principles which are systematically promoted by the IAU; some of which are:

- Education and research is essential to reach all SDGs and the overall ambitious development agenda
- Education as a holistic process that must and should be equitable, accessible, especially to the vulnerable and under-represented and at all levels, including at the HE level.
- Recognition that access is but the first step and that the quality of the offer and the success of those who enter the educational system at all levels are the ultimate goals
- A view of education that ensures that all citizens, in all nations, gain a strong sense of responsibility for the challenges facing humanity and the planet.

According to IAU, equity and inclusion in HE are often overshadowed by excellence and competitiveness. The notion of quality is always expressed in terms of university rankings in the various global league tables, while international collaboration is often quantified in terms of number of mobile students. Consequently, attaining goal 4 of the SDGs would mean that higher education be seen as serving a broader purpose beyond economic development. That is, its contributions must be seen to combat international disparities, and persistent gaps in the availability of education for millions of students. International cooperation should be seen as a way of building institutional capacity to global standards that will make students choose to stay at home for university education.

Inclusive and sustainable higher education should be seen to contribute to: social cohesion, inter-cultural understanding, peace and security as well as the search for more sustainable production methods and consumption practices (AIU, 2015). For the IAU there can be no sustainable quality education at the tertiary level without consideration of wider societal responsibilities. This social responsibility is what brings universities to contribute not only to ensuring inclusive quality education but to sustainable development as a whole.

Expectations of an inclusive-sustainable higher education system

Considering that inclusion is a key indicator of quality education, inclusive-sustainable higher education, therefore, seeks to improve quality in terms of equal access, quality participation in the teaching-learning process and respect for diversity within the physical learning environment.

Equal & improved access

The Glossary of Education Reform (2014), considers access as the approaches adopted by educational institutions and government through policies to ensure or strive to ensure that all learners, no matter their physical, social, economic and political statuses have equal and equitable opportunities to take full advantage of their education. Equal and increased access generally demands that institutions provide additional services or dismantle any actual or potential barriers that might hinder some group of persons from enrolling and participating equitably in certain courses or the entire academic process. Ainscow and Sandill (2010) add that obstacles to inclusive learning are found in all aspects of local and national policies. For UNESCO (2010), the adoption of inclusive education as a vital educational policy was prompted by the need for social justice, equity and equality.

Consequently, to establish an inclusive-sustainable HE system or institution in terms of equal access, decision-making stakeholders and management must have the political will to take deliberate steps towards inclusive policy formulation and adjustments towards increased access. This must be seen in their willingness to do an in-depth analysis of the size and character of the out-of-school populations and ensure that they are integrated into quality education and training programs and institutions. Such analysis would frequently require improved data systems and methods (UNESCO, 2005b, 2009). Policy formulation or adjustments must not only be read on paper but also seen to be fully implemented across the board. This is to ensure that no qualified individual willing to enroll or seek any opportunity within a university is hindered based on race, religion, gender, sexual orientation, disability, stereotyping, special education status, and family income levels amongst others (Ngwa, 2012). These factors are contributors to less “access” to educational opportunities for affected students, thereby undermining the inclusive and sustainable disposition of the said institution. Equal access in this case is considered in terms of breaking any policy and enrollment barriers in HE for persons with special needs and vulnerable persons.

One of the major policy factors that have continued to play against access to higher education in Sub-Saharan Africa has been the lack of funding for socio-economically vulnerable students. Workable inclusive systems or institutions in nations like the United States have put in place positive discrimination policies to handle such

situations. For instance, Barr (2004) in his economic theory of higher education funding notes that there are very poor minority populations in the country with excellent post-primary education attainments which have to be empowered and promoted through the provision of access to HE. Thus, governments need to take action in promoting access through the creation of special scholarship programmes for such groups of citizens. This is because, the ability of such groups to qualify for HE is by their attainment, considering their minority. Consequently, providing those with skilled knowledge/ training (human capital) through a minority or special HE scholarship program would be useful to both the state and their individual developments; thereby ensuring an inclusive process for Sustainable development (Ngwa & Fonkeng, 2017).

Quality participation in the teaching-learning process

Ensuring quality participation in the teaching-learning process within an inclusive higher education institution will require a positive change in attitude by institutional stakeholders (staff, students and administration) towards inclusion, and deliberate adaptations/adjustments in curriculum content and pedagogy in order to capture the needs of all the students. UNESCO (2004) and Wiles and Bondi (2011) note that, an inclusive approach to curriculum content and practice must acknowledge the fact that; while a learner has multiple needs - even more so in situations of vulnerability and disadvantage, every learner should as a matter of inclusive policy, benefit from a commonly accepted basic level of quality education. This justifies a common curriculum that is useful to the learner while also being taught using flexible teaching methods. Accessible and adaptable curricula and learning materials can serve as key to creating inclusive universities (Ainscow et al. 2006; Ainscow & Sandhil, 2010).

UNESCO (2009) and Nyugap and Ngwa (2015) argue that a good number of university curricula expect all students to be taught the same things in their different programs at the same time, and by the same means and methods. Nevertheless, university students have diverse skills and needs. It is therefore necessary that the curricula be flexible enough for possible adjustment to individual needs. This will go a long way to motivate teachers to look for solutions that can be matched with the abilities, learning styles and needs of every student or group of students.

The inclusive education innovation brings to focus some aspects of the regular education setting in terms of organizing and arranging teaching. While educational institutions are expected to have appropriate and desirable common goals for students to achieve, the demands for different academic courses should be viewed within the context of individual students' opportunities and needs (UNGEI, 2010).

The social makeup of universities and lecture rooms in this era of inclusion is changing, particularly in developing nations. More learners are getting access to institutions of learning at all levels. Multi-ability, multi-age and grade classrooms are an increasing reality in most places. It therefore becomes necessary that adapted teaching-learning methods and strategies in diverse contexts be developed and analysed to guarantee a smooth teaching-learning process (Uchem & Ngwa, 2014).

UNESCO (2007) and UNGEI (2010) add that going inclusive at all levels of education calls for proper capacity development for staff in inclusive teaching-learning standards. This involves training on developing inclusive learning materials and learner-centered teaching methods. The use of ICTs and new technology constitute a part of contemporary societies and should be accorded due consideration to ensure quality participation in the teaching-learning process. The capacities of teaching staff and non-teaching staff must be upgraded to enable them to get ready to assist all learners in the learning process. Flexible teaching-learning methods and strategies require a shift from theoretical pre-service-based teacher training to continuous in-service teachers' professional. According to Wiles and Bondi (2011), one individual must not be given all the specific knowledge and competence but several specialisations are required to work with and support ordinary institutional staff. To ensure quality, staff status,

welfare and professional development must be adequately addressed and a standard inclusive staff recruitment and development policy put in place to get qualified manpower to run the institutions.

There is also a need to carefully identify emergency unique situations and settings that cater for learners' needs accordingly. For example, situations of educational emergencies, such as refugee situations must be adequately addressed to ensure quality participation in the teaching-learning process. This will demand that the institutions be provided with multicultural settings and resources needed in refugee and emergency education situations (UNESCO, 2005b & 2009).

Respect for diversity within the physical learning environment

Students with physical disabilities constitute a good number of students with special needs not only in HE institutions but also in other educational establishments. The respect for diversity within the physical learning environment is therefore absolute in implementing sustainable inclusive education practices in HE. There is a need for the physical environment to be accessible for students with special needs within university institutions and the external society. The success of this group of students in their educational pursuit is not only dependent on the pedagogic adjustments but also on the type of physical environment they are exposed to. (Izuka, 2010 and Ngwa, 2012). Persons with disabilities notably those with muscular disabilities, broken bones, amputees and visual impairment need a mobility-friendly physical environment - free from architectural barriers, and consisting of landmarks to ease mobility and access to every department or building of the institution (Nyugap and Ngwa, 2015). Article 5 of the UN Standard Rules on the Equalization of Opportunities for Persons with Disabilities, as one of the policy documents on inclusion notes that the implementation of measures to remove obstacles to participation in the physical learning environment for persons with mobility issues should be the major priority of member states. These measures should include among others the enactment of contextual legislation to ensure accessibility to different areas of society, including housing, schools and public buildings and services, and outdoor environment. Construction engineers and architects involved in the design and construction of public infrastructure should be able to have access to information on disability and accessibility measures for persons with mobility problems (UN, 1993).

Given that inclusive education cannot be practised in a disability and mobility-unfriendly physical environment, Simon and Alverdyan (2009), adapting from the UN Standard Rules, have presented some measures which must be taken into consideration to ensure an enabling physical environment in inclusive learning institutions. These measures include:

- Ensure the construction of ramps with concrete or wood where there are stairs/stairways or make available persons to assist learners with mobility problems in mobility around such areas on campuses.
- The angles of ramps should respond to construction norms, preferably not steeper than 1.8m or at the very least should not be dangerously steep.
- Paint a white line at the edge of each step to improve visibility for those with low vision.
- Ensure that doorways are wide enough, with flat under for wheelchairs to pass through.
- Ensure the accessibility of toilets by making provisions for those with visual impairment, and those in wheelchairs through the putting of handrails, and enough space.
- Enough space in classrooms and lecture halls to ensure wheelchair accessibility.
- Ensure that students with mobility problems are provided with a common accommodation on campuses.

- Putting in place landmarks in major junctions, corners and directions on campuses to facilitate mobility, especially for the visually impaired students.

Providing these especially in universities thus makes the physical learning environment conducive and accommodating for students with disabilities and other mobility problems, thereby reducing fatigue and other negative consequences (Alverdyan, 2009).

Recommendations

On the basis of the above examination, we earmark the following recommendations:

- There is a burning need for all higher education stakeholders to embark on a practical implementation of the laudable national and international policies on inclusive education. There is no gain in ratifying international inclusive education legislations and contextualising them in the National Policy on Education without practical steps towards implementation. Taking such a step will not only require a strong political will by political stakeholders but also moral responsibility and pressure from all education stakeholders who desire an inclusive and equitable educational system.
- The development of a comprehensive Sustainable Inclusive Higher Education Implementation Strategy (SIHEIS) by stakeholders could be a good starting point before any other step can follow. Figure 3 illustrates the content of a possible SIHEIS for adoption by policy implementers within the Nigerian education sector.

Figure 3: Sustainable Inclusive Higher Education Implementation Strategy (SIHEIS)

Source: Authors (2022)

Conclusion

The paper examined the inclusive education nexus for sustainable public higher education in Nigeria. It captured an introduction, a conceptual and theoretical examination of the inclusive education innovation, the inclusive education-sustainable higher education nexus in terms of access, quality participation in teaching-learning and respect for diversity in the physical learning environment. It recommended practical steps towards the implementation of inclusive education legislation in Nigeria. It is established from theoretical and empirical literature that inclusive education is a key indicator of quality higher education, and also a key driver of sustainability in the 21st century. Consequently, as the advocacy for sustainability continues, educational stakeholders at all levels across Nigeria must be compelled as a matter of political and moral will to take practical steps towards the implementation of the inclusive education agenda particularly in the higher education sector and the entire system of education as a whole.

References

- Aina, T. A. (2010). Beyond reforms: The politics of higher education transformation in Africa. *African Studies Review*, 53(1), 21-40.
- Ainscow, M., Booth, T. and Dyson, A., with Farrell, P., Frankham, J., Gallannaugh, F. Howes, A. and Smith, R. (2006). *Improving Schools, Developing Inclusion*. London, Routledge.
- Barr, N. (2004). Higher education funding. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*, 20 (2), 264-283
- Bawakiyillenou, S., Akoto, O. S., Achiadeke, C., Aryeetey, B. E. and Agbe, E. K. (2013). *Higher Education and Industrial Development in Ghana*: International Growth Centre (IGC)
- Brundtland Report, (1987). *Our Common Future: Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development*. United Nations, available at: www.undocuments.net/wced-ocf.htm
- Cleveland, C.J. and I. Kubiszewski (2007). United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED), Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, *Encyclopaedia of Earth*. Available at: http://www.eoearth.org/article/United_Nations_Conference_on_Environment_and_Development
- Elder, J. L. (2009). Higher education and the clean energy, green economy. *EDUCAUSE Review*, 44(6), 108-109.
- Elkington, J. (1994). Towards the sustainable corporation: Win-win-win business strategies for sustainable development. *California Management Review*, 36 (2), 90-100.
- Fakolade, A. O. (2009). Attitude of Teachers towards the Inclusion of Special Needs Children in General Education Classroom: the case of selected schools in Nigeria. *International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education*, 1 (3). Available on: www.iejec.com
- Fonkeng, G. E and Ntembe, A. N. (2009). Higher education and economic development in Africa: The case of Cameroon. *Educational Research and Review*, 4 (5), 231-246 Available online at: <http://www.academicjournals.org/ERR>
- Garuba, A. (2003). Inclusive Education in the 21st Century: Challenges and opportunities for Nigeria. *Asia Pacific Disability Rehabilitation Journal*, 14(2): 191-200.
- IAU (2015). Notes for a Statement on the Framework for Action – Education 2030 For High-Level Meeting, 4 November 2015. UNESCO: Paris
- Izuka, I. (2010). *Inclusive Education in Higher Education*. Being a Keynote Address on the Investiture of the UNESCO Chair at the University of Buea, Buea, Cameroon from 29-30th May 2010.
- Johnston, A. (2007). *Higher education for sustainable development: Final Report of International Action Research Project*: Forum for the Future.
- Karangwa, J. (2010). *The Development of Inclusive Higher Education in Rwanda*. Enabling Education. Available on: [www.eenet.org.uk/.page 5 PHP/](http://www.eenet.org.uk/.page%205%20PHP/)
- Longshurt, J. (2014). *Higher education for sustainable development. Guidance for UK education providers*. The Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education.
- Louw, W. (2013). Green Curriculum: Sustainable Learning at a Higher Education Institution. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning*, 4(1), 1-15

- Ngwa, E. S. (2012). *Assessment of Inclusive education policy implementation at the universities of Ibadan, Nigeria and Buea, Cameroon*. University of Nigeria Nsukka: Unpublished M.Ed theses.
- Ngwa, E. S. and Fonkeng, E. (2017). Indigenous Funding Strategies for Sustainable Higher Education in Nigeria. *African Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(3), 25- 44.
- Ngwa, E. S. and Fonkeng, G. (2017). Indigenous Funding Strategies for Sustainable Higher Education in Cameroon. *African Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(3), 25 – 44.
- Nyugap, C. R and Ngwa, E. S. (2015). Assessing the satisfaction of persons with disabilities, with inclusive education practices in Cameroon’s public Universities. *African Journal of Special Education*, 1(3), 37 – 45.
- Nyugap, C. R. (2017). Comparative Analysis of Inclusive Assessment Procedures of Cameroon General Certificate of Education Board and Nigeria’s National Examination Council. *African Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(3), 45 – 66.
- The Glossary of Education Reform (2014). *Access*. Available on: <https://www.edglossary.org/access/>
- Uchem, R. and Ngwa, E. S. (2014). Inclusive Education Policy Implementation in Post-Apartheid South Africa: Lessons for Nigeria and Cameroon. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 5(36), 92 – 100.
- Uchem, R., Ngwa, E.S., and Asogwa, Uche (2014). Inclusive Education and Sustainable Peace in Africa. *International Affairs and Global Strategy*, 19, 48 – 54.
- UN, (1993). *The Standard Rules on the Equalization of Opportunities for Persons with Disabilities*. Available at: www.un.org/./dirre.oo.htm.
- UN, (2009). *Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities*: UN. Available at: www.un.org/disabilities
- UNESCO (2004). *Changing Teaching Practices: Using curriculum differentiation to respond to students’ diversity*. Paris, UNESCO.
- UNESCO (2005). *Guidelines for Inclusion: Ensuring Access to Education for All*. Paris, France: UNESCO.
- UNESCO (2005b). *UN Decade of Education for Sustainable Development: 2005-2014* UNESCO- Education for Sustainable Development. Available at: www.unesco.org/education/desd
- UNESCO (2007). *The State of Education in Latin America and the Caribbean: Guaranteeing Quality Education for All*: UNESCO-OREALC Regional Bureau for Education in Latin America and the Caribbean.
- UNESCO (2008). *Reinventing Higher Education toward Participatory and Sustainable Development*. Paris: UNESCO.
- UNESCO (2009). *Policy Guidelines on Inclusion in Education*: UNESCO.
- UNESCO, (2006b). *World enrolment of tertiary education in World Bank countries*. Available at: <http://www.upo.unesco.org>.
- UNESCO. (2006). *World Declaration on Education for All*: Available on: www.unesco.org/education/efa/somtien_declaration.
- UNESCO. (2011). *EFA Global Monitoring Report: The hidden crisis – Armed Conflict and Education*: UNESCO.
- United Nations Girls’ Education Initiative (UNGEI), (2010). *Equity and Inclusion in Education: A guide to support education sector plan preparation, revision, and appraisal*. World Bank.
- United Nations World Summit (2005). *2005 World Summit Outcome*, available at: www.un.org/en/ga/search/view_doc.asp?symbol=A/RES/60/1.
- UNO (2015). *Transforming our world: the 2030 agenda for sustainable development*: United Nations General Assembly.
- Wiles, W. & Bondi, C. (2011). *Curriculum Development. A Practical Guide*: Pearson.
- Udandarao, C. L. R & Kuchibhotla, R. (2016). *Triple Bottom-Line Reporting: An Exemplar of Sustainability*. Retrieved in August 2020 from: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/Delivery.cfm/SSRN_ID2755224_code1912797.pdf?abstractid=2755224&mirid=1&type=2